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Preprint · April 2021

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19686.75842

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Effect of Household Water Treatment on Child Diarrhoea in a Low Middle Income Country

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Abstract

Albeit, the progress that has been made on access to improved water coverage in Ghana. Many households are still drinking unsafe water at the household level, leading to more than 5,000 deaths among children under-five years due to diarrhoea. Meanwhile, treated water at the household level is critical for eliminating child diarrhoea. We examined household water treatment and child under-five diarrhoea in Ghana. We extracted the data from 2014 Ghana Demographic and Health Survey and 5,301 were sampled with a complete data on diarrhoea. Probit and Endogenous Treatment Effect (ETE) Models were fitted to examined the effect of improved water supply, improved sanitation facility, and household treated water on diarrhoea reduction. We found that household that treated water at the household and has access to improved sanitation facility like flush toilet is 30 percent and four percent less likely to suffer from the risks of diarrhoea. However, we found that drinking from improved water source rather increase the risk of suffering from diarrhoea by three percent and was consistent in the two models adopted. We also found that household water treatment practices are driven by distance travel to water source, educational attainment, wealth status, and residence. We recommend that the Health Promotion Unit of Ghana Health Service through Community Nurses and the Community-Based Health Planning and Services, should advocate and intensify education programs on household water treatment and proper sanitation practices, especially, for the rural dweller, least educated, and younger mothers in order to curb child diarrhoea.

Keywords: Household water treatment, child diarrhoea, Ghana.

JEL classification: D1, I12, I15

1. Introduction

An essential cog of human capital, which supports workers' productivity, enhance physical capacities, and mental capabilities is health. As the World Health Organization reported in 2006, the quality of every country's future human capital largely depends on health. Literature also suggests that, child health is a key determinant to achieve country's future human capital (World Bank, 2006). This emphasis is placed on why reducing child under-five mortality is considered as a crucial part of the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) - "to end all preventable deaths by 2030".

However, globally, millions of children die every year as a result of diarrhoea. In 2017 alone, the World Health Organization reported 1.7 million deaths of under-five due to diarrhoea (WHO, 2017). Also, recent report from the UN Inter-Agency Group for Child Mortality

Estimation (UN-IGME, 2018) indicated that 6.3 million children and young adolescent died from diarrhoea. Of more concern is that, out of the 6.3 million, children under five years constituted 5.4 million, including 2.5 million deaths occurring in the first month of life, 1.6 million at age 1-11 months, and 1.3 million at age 1-4 years. Of more concern is the low-middle-income countries, where the most episodes of the diarrhoea disease among children under-five years are experienced (WHO, 2017).

Diarrhoea as a disease had compromised many children lives, particularly, under-five years, by limiting their capacity and killing them. In 2016, diarrhoea disease was ranked as the fifth leading cause of death among children under-five years causing about 446 000 deaths (Troeger et al., 2018). Though, numerous interventional programs have been implemented, diarrhoea is still considered as the major killer of under-five years children and low-middle-income countries records the highest rates (Van Malderen, *et al.*, 2019).

In Ghana, under-five mortality is pegged at 52 deaths per 1000 lives birth (see figure 1 below) and this is a critical issue of concern. Despite, the efforts to reduce child mortality rate, a recent study that surveyed of 46 African countries, including Ghana indicated that Ghana is among the eight countries that are making very little progress towards the reduction in under-five mortality (Kipp, et al., 2016). Overall, unsafe water and poor sanitation are the major cause of these deaths. Recent evidence had shown that more than 5,000 children under-five years die every year in Ghana due to diarrhoea which is caused by unsafe water and poor sanitation (iDE, 2017).

Fig. 1: The current trends of childhood mortality in Ghana from 1988-2017.

Source: Ghana Statistical Services (2017).

Despite the fact that safe drinking water and sanitation are basic human rights as recognised by the United Nations (UN, 2010), over 700 million children under-five years die each year globally and 90 percent is mainly caused by unsafe water and poor sanitation (UNICEF & WHO (2018). Despite, according to UNICEF, WHO and World Bank (2015), Ghana has made a substantial progress in providing improved water supply to more than eighty percent of its populations. However, many households, particularly, the rural dweller remains inaccessible to safe water supply. This is because about 60 percent of Ghana's water bodies are contaminated and critical due to the widespread illegal mining (Yeleliere, combine & Duwiejuah, 2018). Also, about

29 percent of all hand pumps are broken while 49 percent partially working in the rural areas (Safe Water Network, 2015).

These evidences highlight the limitations of the indicator for improved water supply. As Gundry et al. (2004) indicated, access to improved water supply does not usually guarantee full access to safe water supply at the point-of-use because there is the possibility of contamination or recontamination during transportation. As a recent study by Amponsah and Mensah (2017) found that improved water sources rather increases the likelihood of contracting diarrhoea by 1.3 percent.

Several studies such as (Clasen, 2007; Clasen et al., 2007a; Zin et al., 2013; Clasen et al., 2015; Capuno et al., 2012; Usman et al., 2016; Allawala et al., 2017) have proven that household water treatment help the individual to take full responsible of water quality. Also, household water treatment is proven to hold much significance as defensive behaviour for diarrhoea disease prevention. For, instance, according to Clasen et al. (2015) treated water at the point-of-use, using technologies like boiling, chlorination, flocculation, filtration, or solar disinfection enhance water quality leading to diarrhoea reduction

However, in Ghana, the perceived benefits from household water treatment is still underscored by researchers. Despite, studies such as (Quinn, 2009; Nkansah, 2014; Essilfie, Padi & Addor, 2017; and Nketia-Amponsah & Mensah, 2017) exist as efforts to increase health literacy in diarrhoea disease transmission dynamics, risks and prevention measures, they mainly focused only improved water and sanitation only neglecting household treated water. Therefore, evidence on household water treatment and diarrhoea is rare in formal research in Ghana. It is against this backdrop in literature that this study examined the effect of household water treatment on child under-five diarrhoea in Ghana.

The research question presented as: (1) what is the effect of improved water source of drinking water child diarrhoea status, (2) what is the effect of household water treatment on child diarrhoea status? and (3) what is the effect of household improved sanitation facilities on child diarrhoea? The rest of the paper is structured as follows: the next section reviews related studies; section three discusses the methods that were adopted for study; section four presents the findings and discussions and section five concludes with recommendations.

1.1 Literature Review

There are multiple pathways that cause diarrhoea disease (WHO, 2009). However, the primary causes are infectious agents from human or animal faeces through the faecal-oral route. Modes of water-related disease transmission includes ingestion of contaminated food or water (through flies, bad sanitation, sewage systems and water treatment systems, poor personal hygiene, cleaning food with contaminated fluids) any direct contact with infected faeces, person to person contact and poor personal hygiene (WHO, 2009).

According to Esrey et al. (1991) access to water, sanitation and hygiene facilities reduces the incidence of a variety of waterborne diseases, such as diarrhoea, intestinal helminthes, guinea worm, skin diseases, and trachoma by interrupting or reducing the transmission of pathogenic disease agents particularly among under-five children. In addition, contaminated water and inadequate sanitation as well as poor hygiene are key drivers of faecal-oral disease transmission, including diarrhoea disease, which is considered to be the most significant public health concern, especially in developing countries.

As shown in Table 1 below, the possible pathogens transmission routes and a wider description of disease burden are associated with poor and inadequate water supply and sanitation.

This is to explain that diarrhoea disease that is associated with waterborne or water-washed disease is also caused by the ingestion of contaminated water or faeces containing pathogenic agents. Given this implication, adopting household water treatment practices such as boiling, chlorination, flocculation, filtration, and solar disinfection, performed mainly at home can enhance drinking water's microbiological quality and reduces the pathogens that causes water contamination to food and the human body.

Table 1: Transmission routes of pathogens and classification of water-related diseases

Classification	Transmission route	Example of diseases transmitted
Waterborne	Through ingestion of pathogens in drinking water	Diarrhoea diseases Enteric fevers, such as typhoid Hepatitis A
Water-washed	Through incidental ingestion of pathogens in the course of other activities; results from having insufficient water for bathing and hygiene	Diarrhoea diseases Trachoma Scabies
Water-based	Through an aquatic invertebrate host; results from repeated physical contact with contaminated water	Guinea worm Schistosomiasis
Water-related insect vector	Through an insect vector that breeds in or near water	Malaria (parasite) and Yellow fever (virus)

Source: Adapted from Bradley, (1977).

Also, Wagner and Lanoix (1958) illustrated the F-diagram that shows the various transmission routes through which pathogens can reach the human body (see figure 2 below). As Wagner and Lanoix (1958) suggested, the F-diagram, household water treatment is a secondary intervention that is extremely significant when it comes to diarrhoea prevention. Other studies like Clasen (2006), established that treated water at the household level is very effective in diarrhoea reduction, indicating that it reduces diarrhoea by 60 percent. Capuno and Carlos (2012) also conducted a study on household drinking water treatment and child diarrhoea in Philippines and confirmed that it decreases the proportion of children under five years with diarrhoea by 4.26 percentage points.

Fig. 2: The “F-diagram” showing the pathways of fecal diseases transmission

Source: Wagner and Lanoix (1959).

Similarly, a recent study by Clasen et al. (2015) on the effectiveness of interventions to improve water quality for preventing diarrhoea found that household water treatment practices such as disinfection products, chlorination products, and filtration systems improve drinking water quality for diarrhoea reduction. Allawala et al. (2017) investigated the effectiveness of household water treatment on the prevalence of diarrhoea diseases reduction in Pakistan and also confirmed that exhibiting household defensive mechanisms (i.e. household water treatment) reduces the risk of child diarrhoea disease by 31.5 percent.

In Ghana, Quinn (2009) found improved sanitation in reducing diarrhoea, but pipe-borne water which is improved water source not significant in diarrhoea reduction. On the other hand, Dekoleadenu (2015) found both improved toilet facilities such as flush toilet and pipe-borne water not significant in reducing diarrhoea among children under five years. In addition, a recent study by Nketiah-Amponsah and Mensah (2017) on the relationship between a sources of drinking water and the prevalence of child under-five years diarrhoea found that drinking from improved water sources rather increases the likelihood of contracting diarrhoea by 1.3 percent. Despite, household water treatment is critical in diarrhoea prevention, however, after a thorough review, there is no evidence on household water treatment and diarrhoea.

Meanwhile, literature (Clasen & Bastable, 2003; and Gundry et al., 2006) suggest that access to improved water supply alone may not be enough to ensure better health outcomes, because there is the possibility that the improved water at the source can be contaminated or recontaminated during transportation, or during handling due to longer distance travel to get to the water source. In other words, availability of improved sources does not guarantee safety for drinking at the household level.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Research Design

The study was deeply rooted in the positivist philosophy which propose that in doing research, values should be driven out, and the methodological approach they propose in achieving value-free research is quantitative (Patten & Newhart 2017, p.32).

2.2 Data source

The study used the 2014 Demographic and Health Survey in Ghana. This survey covers wider range of maternal and child health conditions in Ghana. The GDHS form part of the DHS programme which monitors health indicators in over 90 lower-middle-income countries. The DHS programme aim to enhance global understanding of health and population situation in low-middle-income countries. Collection and dissemination of nationally representative and accurate data on maternal and child health have been part of the aims of the DHS programme since 1984 (GSS, 2015; UNAIDS, 2017)

Ethics Statement

The DHS is available to public on (www.measuredhs.org) on a simple request for registration-access, so no need to obtain further ethical clearance elsewhere. The review and approved protocol of the dataset was already sought by the Ethical Review Committee of the Ghana Health Service and the ICF International Institutional Review Board where the informed consent was collected verbally from respondents prior to interviewing them (GSS, 2015)

2.3 Measures of variables

Dependent variable: Child under five diarrhoea status was the outcome variable measured from the questions asked if the child had experienced diarrhoea within the past two weeks preceding the survey and the response categories of the variable was captured as: “Yes” and “No” as noted by previous studies (Essilfie, Padi & Addor, 2017; Allawala, Barry, Kayani & Lohano, 2017; Kumi-Kyereme & Amo-Adjei, 2016). The ‘Yes’ was coded as ‘1’ and the ‘No’ coded as ‘0’, indicating a dummy variable with ‘1’ for children that experienced diarrhoea and ‘0’ for otherwise.

Independent variable: With respect to the explanatory variables, twelve explanatory variables were used: household treatment of water, household main source of water, household type of toilet facility, child's age, child's sex, child's birth type, disposal of child's stool, mother's age, mother's education level, wealth status, residence, and region. These variables were chosen following previous studies (Essilfie, Padi & Addor, 2017; Allawala, Barry, Kayani & Lohano, 2017).

However, household water treatment, household main source of water, type of toilet facility were the key variables of interest. Household water treatment was dichotomised into two categories, thus, (‘Yes’), coded as 1 if water was treated before drinking in home and (‘No’) coded as 0 if water not treated. Concerning household main sources of water and toilet facility variables, following the WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Program classification (2017), a dummy variable was generated with (‘improved’) coded as 1 and (‘unimproved’) coded as 0 as shown in table 2 below.

Table 2: Definition and classification of water supply and sanitation facilities

<i>Improved’ sources of drinking water</i>	<i>‘Unimproved’ sources of drinking water</i>
Piped water, boreholes or tube wells, protected dug wells, protected springs, rainwater, and packaged delivered water.	Unprotected dug well, unprotected Spring, river, dam, lake, pond, stream, Canal and irrigation canal
<i>‘Improved’ sanitation</i>	<i>‘Unimproved’ sanitation</i>
Flush/pour flush to piped sewer systems, Septic tanks or pit latrines; ventilated improved Pit latrines, composting toilets or Pit latrines with slabs.	Pit latrines without a slab or platform, Hanging latrines or bucket latrines and open defecation.

Source: WHO/UNICEF JMP (2017).

Statistical analyses

STATA 14 MP (Stata Corp, College Station, TX, USA) was used throughout for the descriptive and inferential analysis. The descriptive results were presented in percentages while the bivariate results presented using Pearson chi-square and Cramer's V statistics tests to check for the association between the explanatory variables and child diarrhoea. The Pearson chi-square test was used to check whether or not two or more sample groups are independent, while the Cramer's V statistics was used to examined the extent of the association where a coefficient of 0.03 upwards considered to be high. For the multivariate regression two binary regression models were used and

the marginal effect results presented to establish the specific attributes of the significant explanatory variables which contribute to the prevalence of diarrhoea among the children under five in Ghana.

3.4.2 Empirical strategy

This study focused on exploring the effect of household water treatment on under-five diarrhoea, hence a probit regression model and endogenous treatment effect (ETE) model were fitted to analyse the data at the multivariate level. These models are apt for binary dichotomous outcomes such as diarrhea coded as 1 or 0. The model is expressed below, where f is the probability density function (pdf); ϕ is the standard normal distribution function given as $Z_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$, $\varepsilon \sim f(0,1)$ with no restrictions impose on η .

$$Y^* = X' \beta + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$Y^* = \begin{cases} 1 = \text{yes,} & \text{if } Y^* > 0 \\ 0 = \text{no,} & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\pi = \phi(\eta) = \phi(z' \beta), \quad (3)$$

$$F = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^Y e^{-z^2} dz = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{(\beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i)} e^{-z^2} dz \quad (4)$$

However, methodologically household treated water may be endogenous as Capuno and Tan (2012) posited. According to Capuno and Tan (2012), if the endogeneity is not controlled for, the effect of treated water on child diarrhoea may be biased and may not reflect the true effect of water treatment status on diarrhoea reduction. Endogeneity, according to Wooldridge (2010) can be caused by: i) reverse causality (simultaneity bias), ii) omitted variables bias and iii) measurement errors. Omitted variable bias may occur when an unobserved characteristic, like distance travel to get to water source or risk aversion may drive household water treatment and diarrhoea simultaneously. Therefore, we adopted the endogenous treatment effect (ETE) model to control the potential endogeneity. This ETE model uses a latent factor framework to estimate the parameters using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) techniques (Heckman, 1976; 1978; Maddala, 1983). The mathematical expression of the model is presented as:

$$Y_j^* = \delta T_j + X_j \beta_1 + \varepsilon_j$$

$$Y = \begin{cases} 1 = \text{yes,} & \text{if } Y^* > 0 \\ 0 = \text{no,} & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$T = \begin{cases} 1 = \text{yes,} & \text{if } T^* > 0 \\ 0 = \text{no,} & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where Y_j^* is the outcome variable representing under five diarrhoea. X_j for the covariates and are assumed to be unrelated or exogenous to the error terms. T_j is a binary endogenous variable, (i.e. household water treatment) indicating whether if water was treated (yes) coded as 1 and (no) 0 if otherwise. However, in an attempt to produce an estimate of δ , which is the effect of household water treatment, of which there is likelihood that some unobserved factors may induced household's decision whether to treat water or not. Therefore, the use of the simple probit only to estimate the effect of δ would be biased, leading to inappropriate result of household water treatment. Following this rule, the model is expressed as:

$$T_j^* = Z_j \theta + u_j$$

$$T_J^* = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Z_J\theta + u_J > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma^2 & \rho\sigma \\ \rho\sigma & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Where Z_J as a vector of the indicators used in the analysis to describe factors that influence the household's decision to treat water prior to drinking and the error terms ε_J and u_J are assumed to be bivariate normal with zero mean and covariance matrix. Also, T_J^* is the outcome of undertaking the treatment (i.e., water treatment participation) is explained by a binary discrete outcome described by under-five diarrhoea status. The outcome variable includes a vector of explanatory variables depicting respondents' sociodemographic characteristics of the child and the child's mother, such as gender, age, the size of the area of residence, eating habit indicators, and the treatment variable (treated water, non-treated).

In addition to the explanatory variables included, the treatment equation (household water treatment) also encompasses exogenous variables to acknowledge potential endogeneity. In particular, location of main water sources and distance to water sources is supposed to be directly associated with behaviour but seems unlikely to have a direct effect on diarrhoea (Capuno & Tan 2012; Allawala, Barry, Kayani & Lohano, 2017). In this regard, we instrumented household water treatment with these two variables because they can have a key role in the decision to treat water by influencing attitudes towards water treatment at the household level, but it is unlikely to have a direct effect on diarrhoea.

However, the probit model was employed with no assumption for endogeneity issues for the sake of comparison. As result, all analyses are performed separately in order to investigate potential differences in the effects of the main variables of interest on under five diarrhoea. Furthermore, in order to provide a deeper insight into the influence of smoking on body weight, the marginal treatment effects (MTE) are estimated. The MTE are expressed as the average effect of smoking on BMI for individuals who are on the margin of indifference between having decided to smoke or not (Raptou & Papastefanou, 2018).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive of Key Variables

As shown in Table 3 below, we found that 12 percent of Ghanaian children under-five years suffered from a bout of diarrhoea. This is consistent with previous studies (Essilfie, Padi, & Addor, 2017) that 12 percent under five children suffered from diarrhoea where 62 percent were treated with ORT or increased fluids. Based on this result, it was concluded that substantial progress has been made over years. For instance, in 2008, it was estimated that 20 percent of the proportion of children under five were affected with diarrhoea. However, under mortality still poses a critical health issue of concern, given that 52 deaths per 1000 lives birth is capture in the recent Ghana Maternal Health Survey report (2017), which exceeds the SDG target of 25 deaths per 1,000 live births by 2030.

In addition, the study found that 45 percent of Ghanaians use well water as their primary drinking water source, meanwhile, well water is always safe for drinking. Also, 28 percent use pipe-borne water, while 14 percent use bottle or sachet water. As for surface water sources (river,

dam, lake, ponds, drainages, canal, irrigation channels), the study found that 12 percent of Ghanaian households used them. Even though UNICEF/WHO/World Bank (2015) reported more than 80 percent accessed improved water. However, evidence confirmed that, albeit the progress made in providing improved water sources to households, many are still using unsafe water. For instance, recent study by Nketiah and Mensah (2017) found that drinking from these improved water source rather increased diarrhoea by 1.3 percent in Ghana.

Though the study found that 21 percent of households get their water source within premises and this means access to reliable safe water, which is quite considerable. Yet, unsafe remains a critical issue of concern, because, even if water supply was improved at the source due to improved water can contamination. As Clasen and Bastable (2003) as well as Gundry et al. (2006) posited, improved water supply from the source does not guarantee safe water supply at the point-of-use. Because the water can be contaminated or recontaminated during transportation or handling. Especially, the rural households that mostly spent more than 30 minutes before getting access to water source, there is a high possibility that the water be contaminated or recontaminated, hence posing a high-risk child diarrhoea.

Concerning the different types of water treatment systems used in Ghana. The study found that only seven percent of households do practice household water treatment technologies to treat their drinking water at the household level. While the majority (93 percent) do not treat water at all. In terms of the individual treatment methods, it was established that the most common methods practiced by households were cloth straining and boiling with 2.4 and 1.6 percent respectively. And this was followed by let it stand and settle and camphor use with 0.8 percent each been recorded. The analysis clearly demonstrates that for SODIS as a method of treatment no household reported practicing, thereby indicating zero percent. As mentioned earlier, household adoption of water treatment at the household level is low and the possible explanation is there is low awareness for household water treatment since there is no evidence to prove. Also, sanitation is still a critical issue of concern, as the study found that only 13 percent use improved toilet facility (such as flush toilets). While 54 percent relied on latrines; nearly 33 percent of households lived on no toilet facility, indicating that they dependent on open defecation. And these findings are consistent with previous studies such as Nkansah, 2014; Essilfie, Padi, and Addor (2017); Agbadi, Darkwah and Kenney (2019) that the proportion of Ghanaian households with access to flush toilet facilities is only 12 percent.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Results of Some key Variables

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Prevalence of diarrhoea		
No	4659	87.89
Yes	642	12.11
Total	5301	100
Household source of water		
Piped water	1471	27.75
Well water	2375	44.81
Bottle /sachet water	764	14.40
Surface water	615	11.61
Other	76	1.42
Total	5301	100
Water treatment methods		
Boiling	82	1.55

Chlorination	30	0.56
Cloth straining	126	2.37
Filtration	25	0.48
Let it stand and settle	45	0.85
Camphor	45	0.85
Purification	30	0.56
Other	4	0.07
Total	387	7.29
Type of toilet facility		
Flush	710	13.40
Latrine	2855	53.85
No facility	1736	32.74
Total	5301	100

Source: GDHS, 2014

4.2. The Association Between Socio-economic Factors and Child Diarrhoea

Also, Table 4 below, shows the results of the association between socio-demographic factors and under five diarrhoea. Using Pearson Chi square and the Cramer's V statistical tests bivariate were analysed to established the association. Child sex, baby size, mother age and level of education, time spent on water were found to be the major significant socio-economic predictors of child diarrhoea. In addition, household's ccess to improved toilet facilities such as flush was found to be significant and negatively associated to diarrhoea, indication that these facilities reduce diarrhoea. These findings corroborate with previous studies, for instance, Annim *et al.* (2014), contended that children living in households with access to improved toilet facilities like flush toilets have better health outcomes compared to counterparts.

On the other hand, access to improved water was found to be significantly associated to diarrhoea, but positive. Meaning that improved water sources rather increases the likelihood of contracting of diarrhoea disease in Ghana. Which confirms the recent by Nketiah-Amponsah and Mensah (2017), that emphasised that drinking from improved water sources rather increase the odds of diarrhoea by about 1.3 times. The study also conforms to other studies conducted in other countries in relation to access to improved water in recent times not effective in diarrhoea reduction. For example, according to Shaheed *et al.* (2014), the indicator for 'improved' water sources do not necessarily provide safe water several reasons such as location of source, time travel to water source as well as handling of water. Therefore, household access to improved water supply does not directly guarantee household having to access to safe water supply, especially at the household level or point-of-use.

As for the association between type of place of residence and child diarrhoea, it was found that children under five years residing in urban areas are less likely to suffer from the risk of diarrhoea compared to their counterparts in rural areas. And this has been consistently established in previous studies such as (Nkansah, 2014; Adams, Boateng & Ameyaw, 2016; Essilfie, Padi & Addor, 2017; Armah et al., 2018; Agbadi, Darkwah & Kenney, 2019). In the same, the study found regional variations in the incidence of diarrhoea in Ghana. The study established that Brong-Ahafo was the where the highest risk of child diarrhoea happened with 18 percent. And this was followed by the Eastern Region with 16 percent, Northern Region with 15 percent. Ashanti Region with 14 percent as well as Upper West with 14 percent, while Upper East was found to 11 percent.

On the other hand, Volta region 6.67 percent, Western Region, 7.60 percent, Greater Accra Region 7.62 percent, and the Central Region, 9.46 percent were the regions found to report the

lowest prevalence of diarrhoea. And these results are consistent with what was reported the overall 2014 GDHS dataset. Because, from the Ghana Statistical report on GDHS (2014), Brong-Ahafo region was found to be the region that experienced the highest prevalence of diarrhoea with 17 percent. While the Central region, Greater Accra region and Volta regions were the regions that experienced the lowest prevalence of diarrhoea with seven percent respectively.

Moreover, these results were found to be in with consonance with Noora et al (2017), that found that indeed, Brong Ahafo was the region that experienced the highest prevalence of child diarrhoea. They even went further and pointed out that at the end of December, 2014, the Disease Surveillance Unit in Brong-Ahafo region already reported several cases of acute watery diarrhoea in most health across different districts in the region, so there is no doubt that the region recorded the highest prevalence of child diarrhoea. As for the Eastern region preceding Brong- Ahafo region, the possible explanation could be the widespread of illegal mining activities leading to poor quality water sources. And for this reason, most household in most parts of the year, do not have a regular supply of safe water, hence relates to consequences for diarrhoea disease among children, especially the under the age of five years.

Table. 4: Association Between Socio-economic Factors and Diarrhoea

Characteristics	Child under 5 diarrhoea (%)	
	No	Yes
Child's sex		
Male	86.02	13.98
Female	89.52	10.48
Chi ² =15.3257 (0.000), Cramer's V = -0.0533		
Child's age in month		
<6	95.47	4.53
6-8	87.66	12.34
9-11	84.89	15.11
12-17	82.35	17.65
18-23	79.86	20.14
24-35	82.74	17.26
36-47	92.76	7.24
48-59	92.87	7.13
Chi ² = 82.3210 (0.000), Cramer's V = 0.1720		
Child's birth type		
Single	87.85	12.15
Twin	84.28	15.72
Chi ² =2.5840 (0.108), Cramer's V = -0.0219		
Mother's age		
<20	80.63	19.37
20-34	87.88	12.12
35-49	88.11	11.89
Chi ² = 9.2169 (0.010), Cramer's V = 0.0413		

Mother's Educ.		
No education	86.17	13.83
Primary	87.43	12.57
Secondary	88.55	11.45
Tertiary	94.09	5.91
Chi ² = 13.3099 (0.004), Cramer's V = 0.0496		
Time to water source		
On premises	90.00	10.00
<15 minutes	88.37	11.63
15-29 minutes	86.80	13.20
>30 minutes	86.22	13.78
Chi ² = 9.8951 (0.019), Cramer's V = 0.0433		
Quality of water		
Unimproved	90.19	9.81
Improved	86.61	13.69
Chi ² = 18.11148 (0.000), Cramer's V = 0.0501		
Quality of sanitation		
Unimproved	86.92	13.08
Improved	92.92	7.08
Chi ² = 20.0795 (0.000), Cramer's V = -0.0615		
Treatment of water		
Do not treat	87.84	12.16
Yes treated	85.42	14.58
Chi ² = 1.7112 (0.191), Cramer's V = 0.0178		
Area of residence		
Urban	88.01	11.99
Rural	87.48	12.52
Chi ² = 0.3346 (0.563), Cramer's V = 0.0079		
Regions		
Western Region	92.40	7.60
Central Region	90.54	9.46
Greater Accra Region	92.38	7.62
Volta Region	93.33	6.67
Eastern Region	84.32	15.6
Ashanti Region	85.60	14.40
Brong-Ahafo Region	81.69	18.31
Northern Region	85.28	14.72
Upper East Region	89.17	10.83
Upper West Region	85.71	14.29
Pearson Chi ² = 70.4784 (0.000), Cramer's V = 0.1153		

Source: GDHS, 2014

4.3. Factors that influence the households' adoption of water treatment in Ghana

Table 5 illustrate results on related factors that influence the adoption of household water treatment practices. Using the Pearson Chi-square and the Cramer's V statistic, the study established type of water source, time travel to get access to water sources, mother's education, the wealth status significantly and positively influences the adoption of household-based water treatment. Also, the type of place of residence, region of residence influences the decision of households to adopt household-based water treatment. It was established that households in urban area, are about seven percent likely to treat water at home compared to their counterparts at the rural areas.

The implication is that urban households presumably have better access to health information with regards to the health benefits of treating water than that of rural households, hence likely to have knowledge on household water methods as an intervention that is effective in diarrhoea reduction. Also, households in the urban may be headed by highly educated men or mothers, and so have the knowledge on health information regarding the benefits of treating its water before drinking. As Allawala et al. (2017) opined, education level of the mother is a significant factor that influence the decision to adopt household-based water treatment as a defensive mechanism against unsafe water.

Table. 5: Bivariate regression result on factors associated household water treatment

Characteristics	Household treatment of water (%)	
	No	Yes
Area of residence		
Urban	92.96	7.04
Rural	94.32	5.68
Chi ² =4.1161 (0.042), Cramer's V = -0.0276		
Education level		
No education	95.39	4.61
Primary	91.74	8.26
Secondary	93.63	6.37
Higher	91.63	8.37
Chi ² =17.9832 (0.000), Cramer's V= 0.0577		
Wealth status		
Poor	94.02	5.98
Middle	92.52	7.48
Richer	93.33	6.67
Richest	95.15	4.85
Chi ² =10.6833 (0.030), Cramer's V =0.0445		
Sex of household head		
Male	94.24	5.76
Female	92.24	7.76
Chi ² = 6.5193 (0.011), Cramer's V = 0.0347		

Water sources		
Piped/bottled	95.54	4.46
Well	95.30	4.70
Surface water	83.36	16.64
Other sources	80.52	19.48
Chi ² =159.9910 (0.000), Cramer's V=0.1737		
Distance to water source		
On premises	96.18	3.82
Less than 15 minutes	93.30	6.70
15-29 minutes	93.28	6.72
30mins and above	88.12	11.88
Chi ² =55.0657 (0.000), Cramer's V =0.1021		
Region		
Western	96.05	3.95
Central	93.28	6.72
Greater Accra	95.55	4.45
Volta	86.78	13.22
Eastern	91.58	8.42
Ashanti	92.19	7.81
Brong-Ahafo	92.74	7.26
Northern	95.14	4.86
Upper East	96.68	3.32
Upper West	96.96	3.04
Chi ² =70.7995 (0.000), Cramer's V = 0.1145		

Source: GDHS, 2014

4.4 Regression results on the effect of water treatment on child under five diarrhoea

As shown in Table 6 below, the results from both the probit and endogenous treatment effect regression are presented. First of all, the study found improved water supply in both models to be significant but on the average likelihood to increase child diarrhoea by three percent. This indicates that drinking from improved water source rather increases the likelihood of contracting diarrhoea. And this is in consonance with other studies. For instance, Nketiah-Amponsah and Mensah (2017) recently conducted a study and reported that drinking from improved water sources rather increase diarrhoea by 1.3 times. In addition, it confirms Bain et al., (2014) and Martinez-Santos (2017) that access to improved sources of water do not necessarily provide access to safe water as the quality of water or not always be free from contamination.

The possible explanation provided was that the choice of improved water does not adequately address the safety and reliability of drinking water supplies as well as the sustainability of water supply sources as clearly stated. The indicator for improved water sources is been over-emphasized neglecting that most of these sources are not monitored once provided. Another possible explanation could be location of the water source. Because, if the water sources are located far away from the household dwelling, the improved supply water can be contaminated during transportation, even though the water could be improved from the source. Especially, when distance travel to get to water source exceeds 30 minutes, there is high possibility of contaminating water quality. With respect to the effect of household water treatment on diarrhoea, the study found

a significant and positive effect from the probit model indicating that when water is treated at the household-based, it rather increases the likelihood of contracting diarrhoea.

However, intuitively, this result could be biased from ignoring the possible endogeneity, given that there is a causal links between household water treatment and diarrhoea. Therefore, the endogenous treatment effect (ETE) model was adopted with endogeneous regressors such as time to get to water, location of household main source of water and mother's education level to control the possible endogeneity. And when the endogeneity was controlled, treated was found to be significant and negatively related to diarrhoea 5 percent. The study found that on average, households' household-based water treatment likely to reduce child diarrhoea by 30 percent. And this is not different from the recent study by Allawala et al. (2017) that established that treating water prior to drinking is 31.5 percent less likely to report any cases of diarrhoea diseases in the household.

Concerning sanitation, the study found improved toilet facilities in both models to be significant and negatively related to diarrhoea, indicating that household access to improved toilet facilities such as flush toilet facilities likely to reduces diarrhoea disease. From the endogenous treatment model, it was found that households that use improved toilet facility like flush toilet is four percent less likelihood to reduce child diarrhoea. Also, an increase in the age of a child on average likely to reduces child diarrhoea. Moreover, household economic status was found to be significant indicating that the higher the wealth index, the low probability that a child will suffer from diarrhoea.

Mother's education was significant conforming to the Grossman (1972) theory that explains that mothers having high education status could alleviate poor sanitation in order to reduce child diarrhoea. The study found that children whose mother are educated to tertiary level are less likely to suffer from diarrhoea. And this is in consonance to Essilfie (2015) and Maxwell (2013) that reported in their study that children whose mothers are highly educated are less likely to suffer from diarrhoea compared to children whose mothers are uneducated.

Table. 6 Marginal effects for Probit and Endogenous Treatment Effect (ETE) models on diarrhoea

Variable	Probit	ETE
Water Source (base=Unimproved) Improved	0.033*** (0.0112)	0.033*** (0.013)
Treated water (base=No) Yes	0.037* (0.021)	-0.302** (0.171)
Sanitation (base=Unimproved) Improved	-0.032** (0.017)	-0.043** (0.0182)
Stool disposal (base=Unsafe) Safe disposal	-0.008 (0.011)	-0.013 (0.011)
Wealth Status (base=Poorest) Poorer	0.016 (0.014)	
Middle	0.015 (0.017)	
Richer	-0.022	

Richest	(0.019) -0.034 (0.024)	
Mother's Age (base=<20 Years)		
20-34 years	-0.061** (0.0289)	-0.069*** (0.0257)
35 years and Above	-0.063** (0.0297)	-0.071*** (0.0268)
Mother's Education (base=No)		
Primary	-0.008 (0.0135)	-0.007 (0.0138)
Secondary	-0.014 (0.0126)	-0.019 (0.0128)
Higher	-0.056** (0.0243)	-0.039** (0.0321)
Child's Sex (base=Male)		
Female	-0.033*** (0.0088)	-0.036*** (0.0093)
Child's Age	-0.015** (0.0031)	-0.016*** (0.0033)
Child Birth type (base=Multiple)		
Single	-0.044* (0.0255)	-0.052** (0.0235)
Place of Residence (base=Urban)		
Rural	-0.019 (0.0126)	-0.007 (0.0109)
Region (base=Brong-Ahafo)		
Western	-0.086*** (0.0195)	-0.100*** (0.0205)
Central	-0.074*** (0.0193)	-0.075*** (0.0201)
Greater Accra	-0.067*** (0.0232)	0.085*** (0.0233)
Volta	-0.108*** (0.0183)	-0.114 *** (0.0212)
Eastern	-0.007 (0.0226)	-0.009 (0.0208)
Ashanti	-0.009 (0.0228)	-0.017 (0.0212)
Northern	-0.027 (0.0209)	0.037** (0.0192)
Upper East	-0.066*** (0.0206)	-0.076*** (0.0208)
Upper West	-0.037 (0.0224)	-0.047** (0.022)
_cons.		0.357 (0.041)
Stage 2: Treatment of Water		
Location of water (base=Inside dwelling)		
Outside dwelling		4.664 (1.204)
Time to water source		0.005 (0.001)

_cons	-6.389 (1.233)
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Notes *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively
robust standard errors in brackets

Source: GDHS, 2014

5. Conclusions

Despite efforts to increase households' access to improve water supply and health literacy in sanitation as prevention measures against diarrhoea disease transmission dynamics and risks among children, especially under five years. Yet many households still lack access to safe water leading many deaths due to diarrhoea among children under five years. Meanwhile, the perceived barriers still largely underscored adoption household water treatment. This study moved beyond access to improved water and provided information on household water treatment as defensive behaviour for improve uptake of child diarrhoea prevention measures for Ghana.

This study sheds lights the effect of household water treatment for child diarrhoea reduction in Ghana using the 2014 demographic and health survey (DHS). By adopting endogenous treatment effect mode in addressing the possible endogeneity, the study found that households that adopts to treating water are less likely to reduce child under five diarrhoea by 30 percent. Also, children that lived in households with access to improved sanitation facilities such as flush toilet are four percent less likely to suffer from the risk of diarrhoea compared to their counterparts in households that practice open defecation. However, drinking from improved water sources rather increase the likelihood of contracting diarrhoea. Other variables such as mother's education was found to be effective in reducing diarrhoea.

Therefore, the Health Promotion Unit of Ghana Health Service through Community Nurses and the Community-Based Health Planning and Services, should advocate and intensify education programs on household water treatment and proper sanitation practices, especially, for the rural dweller, least educated, and younger mothers. Also, Ghana Water Company should dedicate effort to monitor the quality of drinking water once provided towards the achievement of SDGs goal 3 and 6.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Definition and measurement of variables

Variables	Code	Variable type	Unit (How it was coded)
Water source	Watersource	Dummy	Unimproved=0, Improved=1
Treated water	Treewater	Dummy	No (untreated)=0, Yes(treated)=1,
Sanitation	Sanitationfac.	Dummy	Unimproved=0, Improved=1,
Disposal of stool	Chstool	Dummy	Unsafe=0, Safe=1,
Mother's age	Moage	Continuous	Number: Age in years (15-49)
Mother's education	Moedu	Categorical	No Education=0, Primary=1, SHS=2, Higher=3
Child's Sex	Chsex	Dummy	Male=0, Female=1
Child's Age	Chage	Continuous	Number: Age in months (0-59)
Child's Birthtype	Chbirthtype	Dummy	Single=0, Twin=1
Wealth Index	Wealthindex	Categorical	Poorest=0, Poorer=1, Middle=3, Richer=4, Richest=5
Area of Residence	Area	Dummy	Rural=0, Urban=1
Region	region	Categorical	The ten administrative regions in Ghana

Source: Author's own compilation from literature

Appendix B: Summary statistics of the variable used for the study

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Diarrhoea	5301	0.1230	0.3285	0	1
Improved water	5301	0.8374	0.3690	0	1
Treated water	5301	0.0722	0.2416	0	1
Time to get to water source	5301	20.5641	20.8192	0	180
Improved sanitation	5301	0.1305	0.03369	0	1
Time to toilet facility	5301	19.4107	12.0833	1	120
Male child	5301	0.4785	0.4996	0	1
Child age in years	5301	1.8934	1.4100	0	4
Child age in months	5301	27.88497	17.1625	0	59
Safe disposal of stool	5301	0.29188	0.4547	0	1
Mother's age in years	5301	30.6715	6.8722	15	49
Mother's education	5301	1.13305	0.9428	0	3
Wealth index	5301	2.5240	1.3897	0	5
Single Birth type	5301	0.9576	0.2015	0	1
Rural residence	5301	0.6033	0.4892	0	1
Region	5301	5.6471	2.8371	1	10

Source: GDHS, 2014.

Appendix C: Diagnostic Test for the Two Models

Diagnostic Tests for Probit regression model	
N	5,301
R ²	0.040
Mean VIF	3.20
Linktest	_hat: P> z =0.088* hatsq: P> z =0.782

Diagnostic Tests for Endogenous Treatment Effect model	
N	5,301
Hazard lambda	0.175 (0.081)
Rho	0.521
Sigma	0.337
Wald Test of Indep. Equation: (rho = 0):	chi2=1.02 Prob > chi2 = 0.0310